

Early Career Voices in Arctic Observing: Outcomes from the Polar Early Career World Summit

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This short statement presents the synthesized priorities of polar early career community members, gathered from the Polar Early Career World Summit (PECWS) and multiple modes of online engagement before and after the event. The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) and the Polar Science Early Career Community Office (PSECCO) organized the summit and associated engagement opportunities, engaging 238 polar early career researchers and professionals (ECRs) from across the globe to shape collective priorities for the future of polar research. These perspectives are especially timely as the international community prepares for the 5th International Polar Year (IPY-5) in 2032–2033, offering an unprecedented opportunity for early career contributions to be integrated into global polar science planning.

The PECWS Synthesis Report [1] presents a community-driven vision: a roadmap developed by polar early career professionals that urges the polar research community to rethink systems, value relationships, and strengthen pathways for equitable participation in the lead up to, during, and beyond IPY-5. It highlights not just what research should be pursued, but how we can work together to ensure polar science is impactful, responsible, and resilient in the face of rapid change.

Synthesis process

We started the synthesis process by gathering collective input from the polar early career community, using surveys, workshops, and online engagement to identify 12 priority themes. At PECWS, participants collaboratively identified and refined priorities and developed vision statements for each theme. Based on asynchronous contribution modes before and after PECWS—ensuring the inclusion of perspectives beyond those able to attend in person—the editors incorporated feedback from the broader community to refine the vision and priority statements and subsequently synthesized cross-cutting topics.

Cross-cutting topics

Six cross-cutting topics were established in the PECWS Synthesis Report by identifying topically related priority statements across the 12 theme groups. The presented cross-cutting topics are supported by priority statements from at least four different theme groups, indicating relevance across varied topics of community concern. The cross-cutting topics from the PECWS Synthesis Report are shared below.

Funding system transformation

Current funding structures are inadequate for supporting the collaborative, relationship-based research that polar science requires. There is a strong consensus around the need to more justly distribute funding across diverse communities and groups and to better distribute long-term funding that encourages collaborative resource sharing. Multiple priority statements call for funding cycles that support relationship building, reduce barriers to international collaboration, and eliminate unpaid labor in research. This transformation should reduce institutional gatekeeping in research processes, enabling direct community funding mechanisms.

Honoring multiple ways of knowing and doing

Polar research must move beyond narrow definitions of science to embrace diverse knowledge systems and methodologies. Science should be validated through diverse lenses while building bridges between knowledge systems in ways that honor their distinctions. This includes implementing decolonial methodologies, promoting Indigenous and Traditional Ecological Knowledge, and ensuring that data sovereignty principles protect community knowledge systems.

Community-centered research practices

Research must be restructured to center project co-creation and co-ownership between researchers and parties involved in any stage of the research process. The polar ECR community calls to promote research as a cyclical rather than linear process, better reflecting Indigenous knowledge systems. This includes ensuring community input from conception to completion, implementing trauma-informed practices, and supporting Indigenous data sovereignty. Success in research should be inclusive of non-Western, nonacademic, and non-bibliometric achievements.

Open and accessible science

While supporting open science, the polar ECR community recognizes the need to balance data accessibility with ethical considerations. Data are ideally standardized, readily accessible, and interoperable, and simultaneously uphold Indigenous data sovereignty. Global standards for data sharing should ensure that open science practices do not perpetuate extractive research relationships. Accessibility must extend beyond data to include participation in all stages of research processes and decision-making.

Effectively communicating science

Effective science communication requires moving beyond traditional academic dissemination to embrace diverse formats, audiences, and feedback mechanisms. Groups emphasize the need to employ new modes of engagement to reach the broader public while ensuring that communication is culturally appropriate and accessible. This includes training scientists as effective communicators, establishing clear communication pathways between researchers, policymakers, and communities, and incorporating community feedback as an integral component of the research process.

Ensuring safety and well-being

Safety encompasses physical, mental, and cultural well-being for all contributors to polar research and is particularly relevant to historically marginalized groups. The polar ECR community calls for the prioritization of the mental and physical well-being of polar researchers in addition to the creation of safe and accepting spaces for all. This includes implementing trauma-informed practices, addressing systemic barriers and harassment, and providing culturally appropriate support systems in all stages and places of research. Research processes should not perpetuate harm to communities or individuals. Safety considerations must be integrated into all aspects of research design and implementation.

Conclusion and next steps

PECWS presented an incredible opportunity for the global polar early career community to exchange ideas on what they want the future of polar science to look like as they progress through their careers. Notably, many of the priorities shared in this report are about the *how* of doing research, rather than being specifically about *what* research projects should take place. This framing of priorities developed through PECWS has already been critiqued by some in the polar community as not being relevant to 'how IPY planning has been done in the past', or more specifically, working to define scientific research questions.

The PSECCO and APECS teams see the framing driven by polar ECRs as an opportunity for the entire polar community to do science in a better and more equitable way in the years to come. As organizations whose missions are focused on listening to and uplifting the voices of polar early career researchers, PSECCO and APECS understand how valuable fresh perspectives from polar ECRs are in advocating for new systems of thinking within an already established community.

It is vital that these recommendations from the early career community are taken seriously to ensure that science welcomes everyone into the process, values relationships and collaborations, connects with the public, is environmentally responsible, and helps us to address pressing challenges through valuing interdisciplinarity.

We are asking the participants of the Arctic Observing Summit and the broader scientific community to:

- review the full PECWS Synthesis Report (accessible at pecws.org/synthesis-report) with all 12 vision statements and 75 priorities,
- include these priorities when discussing and planning Arctic observing strategies and activities,
- help implement these priorities in their personal work as well as organisational initiatives, and
- consider endorsing the PECWS Synthesis Report as individuals by visiting pecws.org/support.

Science is a holistic process that encompasses more than just addressing research questions. The polar early career community that engaged in the PECWS process believes that to do the best science we can as a polar research community, we must consider each of the priorities outlined above alongside our science goals and build processes that enable us to tackle urgent science questions responsibly.

References

[1] Dryák-Vallies, M. C., Strand, S. M., Payne, M. R., & Schlindwein, A. (2025). Polar Early Career World Summit Synthesis Report. Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) International Directorate and Polar Science Early Career Community Office (PSECCO). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16994869>